

Religion And Ethnicity: The Need For National Integration In Nigeria

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to examine how religion and ethnicity can help bring about national integration in Nigeria. Nigeria became an independent nation in 1960 with the hope that Nigerians will be integrated with one another for the purposes of co-existence, administration, and development of the nation. But this seems to be difficult. Since the colonial periods and up till now, there have been ethnic and religious crises that made the concept of national integration seem impossible. Ethno-religious crises in Nigeria are deeply rooted and is threatening the very survival of the country as a nation. Often times are intra and inter religious crises. The question is: how can this violence work for national unity, integration and development? It has negative consequences on the socio- economic and political lives of the people. To the extent that matters which ought to have been resolved are unnecessarily ethnicized. It is obvious that the grievances which normally aggravate ethnic religious crises are most often than not revealed through sectarian crises, tribal unrest, bitter political complaints, and violent insurgents, among others. However, the question of national integration is of necessity and not a matter of choice. The study used historical method of analysis for optimal results. The findings reveal that there has been ethnic and religious crises in the country since its inception as an independent nation and the need for the pursuit on the issue in order to proffer lasting solution to check mate the disintegration that may be raised by ethno-religious disturbances. The study recommends among others that the subject of national integration should not be overlooked, but rather it should be encouraged, embraced and put into practice by Nigerians in order to promote unity, integration and national development in the country.

Keywords: Religion, Ethnicity, National Integration, and development.

Introduction

National integration is the awareness of a common identity amongst the citizens of a country. It means that though we belong to different castes,

religions and regions and speak different languages, we recognize the fact that we are all one. The decision which was made by the people of Nigeria prior to independence to become the federal Republic required that the people will be integrated with one

another for the purpose of co-existence, unity, national integration, and development. But this dream seems to be difficult in Nigeria. What seems to exist is the crises of marginalization, ethnic rivalries, and practice of sectional and tribal politics among others. This has negative consequences on the socio-economic and political lives of the citizenry. According to (Ajah, 2012:9) “national integration in Nigeria after independence is an ontological necessity and not a choice”.

Nigeria is a diverse country with about 150 million people, it is multi-cultural, multi-ethnic, multi-religious, and clearly heterogeneous (Ejikeme, 2016). Thus, the beauty and strength of its existence as a nation lie in the variety and unity of its set up. According to Awa (2013), national integration “is a process of creating a sense of national consciousness, uniqueness of identity and loyalty among people of different socio-cultural identities (racial, ethnic, language, religion, and so on) into a single territorial political society”. These diversities are evidently manifested in the citizens’ cultural and religious practices. For instance, there are more than four hundred documented ethnic groups across the country comprising of millions of people who are adherents of the two major religion (Albert, 2012). Nigerians are very religious people though the nation has not adopted any religion as a state religion.

Religion is man’s belief in God and man’s relationship with God. Religions, “many at times depend on symbols and narratives usually employed to offer a meaning to human existence and also to

explain the indices for the creation of the universe” (Alamu, 2006:17). In addition, there are some religions that have ethnical foundations indicating how their adherents should behave in any given society. This must have made Oluniyi (2006:1) to observe that “religion is a source and guarantor of individual and societal peace”. The basic requirement is that the religion being a belief system must be held by a group of people who publicly share its doctrine. Religious beliefs are evident in religious dogma, creed, conviction, doctrine, and principles (Ayantayo, 2009). While religious practices include the worship, prayer, fellowship, and alms giving among others. Adesina (2005:7) is of the opinion “that religious ethics are the mere principles that guide religions and set the standard for what is and isn’t acceptable behavior”. Most Nigerians adhere to the two religions (Christianity and Islam), though it is widely known that there are differences in their understanding of the religions both at the intra and inter group levels. For instance, in spite of the fact that all Muslims are united in their belief of the fundamental pillars of the religion, many of them however differ in their actions, sometimes determined by sectarian variation. The same is similar among the Christians. This is not the problem, rather “the politicization, or outright mischievous projection of these sectarian differences or identities combined with ignorance and deep seated suspicions and stereotypes are what often resulted into violent and conflicts at the intra and inter group levels with severe consequences on the security and integration of the nation” (Pate, 2005).

In recent times, the frequency and occurrence of such conflicts appear to be on the increase in Nigeria and this situation has become worrisome to most Nigerians. Fifty-eight years after independence, Nigerians are still threatened with some unacceptable facts about social reality that continues to dent the integrity and unity of the nation. Especially, ethno-religious violence and fears have literally redefined the understanding and concept of trust as the basis of peaceful co-existence particularly in Northern Nigeria. For instance, “between 1976 and 2009, over 100,000 people had lost their lives and property worth billions of Naira were destroyed in more than fifty recorded ethno-religious conflicts in that part of Nigeria” (News watch, November 2, 2009, Eliagwu, 2004). These conflicts had left traces of political, social, economic, and psychological losses and pains, injured and poisoned established relationships among Nigerians. Gradually, Nigerians of different religions are feeling insecure and highly helpless in some parts of the country. Such conflicts had affected the spirit of unity and integration, which is about peaceful co-existence, unity, and harmony of the diverse people of Nigeria.

Nigeria as a nation since 1960, from all indications has not been able to attain her set objectives of unifying the diverse ethnic groups in all facets of socially, economically, politically, among others. The contributing factors to this reality could be attributed to lack of unity caused by ethnic and religious conflict. Ethnicity started during colonial era and it has had negative effects on Nigerians. For instance, the Action Congress (A.C) was led by late Chief

Obafemi Awolowo, a Yoruba, the NCNC was headed by late Dr. Nnamdi Azikiwe, an Igbo, while the NPC was led by Sir Ahmadu Bello, the Saruana of Sokoto, a Fulani and a Muslim. The leadership of these parties were drawn along ethnic cleavages with their ethnic patterns. All these were products of the colonial administrative arrangement that encouraged ethnic politics in that it divided Nigeria into three regions that is, West-Yoruba, North-Hausa/Fulani and East-Igbo. This division reproduce the three major ethnic groups in the country. It however “opposes secularity which is constitutionally allowed in religious pluralistic societies like Nigeria, it has threatened the stability and development of the nation with a claim to numerical superiority” (Ayantayo, 2012).

On several occasions, political leaders promoted their religious belief to the utmost level of the country’s governance. For example, the elevation of the Sharia into legal and political system, the issue of Nigeria becoming the member of organization of Islamic countries (OIC) among others. There was the formation of the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) (Enwerem, 2005). However, for religion and ethnicity to promote national integration, the popular misconceptions of “religion cannot bring unity should be erased”. In realizing the integrative effort of man in ensuring national integration (Stitch, 2008: 8) affirms that “the agencies of ethnicity and religion must work in close and harmonious co-operation”. This is only attainable in a situation where peaceful co-existence is attained. It can be argued that ethnicity and religion that could have been forces

promoting national integration have failed in achieving this desirable objectives. Thus, the paper examines the persistent incidence of ethno-religious crises in Nigeria and its consequences on socio-economic and political lives of the citizenry.

Features that Account for the Eruption of Ethno-Religious Violence in Nigeria

Illiteracy: This results to insufficient understanding of the teachings of religion. Every religion preaches peace. The Quran discourages Muslims from “caucus arguments with followers of other religions except to invite them to Islam through civility, good words, good manners, and good example” (Aminu, 2003). This suggests that it is forbidden to keep company with people who perpetrate negative acts like corruption, conflict, hatred, killing and other acts which are not the teachings of any religion. With peace, there will be development and national integration.

Politicization of one’s Religion: This relays to individuals in the country who describe their religion or ethnic group as superior or inferior for the sake of access to resources. Wild arguments are thrown on who is the majority, minority, and so on. If not controlled, can degenerate into violence ethnic or religious conflict with its negative consequences on the lives and properties of people. Thus, failure to live in peace leads to destruction. Both Christians and Muslims should shun these senseless conflicts.

Ethnicity/ Tribe: Nothing in Nigeria’s political history captures her problem of national integration more graphically than

the chequered fortune of the word tribe. According to Achebe (1983:5) “tribe has been accepted at one time as a friend, rejected as an enemy at another, and finally smuggled in through the back- door as an accomplice”. Ethnicity which creates feelings of pride or inferiority complex leads to social injustice and serious conflict to any given society. The sentimental feeling of either minority or majority would never help in nation building. Thus, with good citizenship and worship, we shall build a prosperous nation and live as a developing nation. Society, can only develop when there is peaceful co-existence and due regard in our social interactions.

Political Manipulation: This is another cause of ethno-religious crisis in Nigeria. For instance, Babaginda during his regime tried to put Nigeria in Organization of Islamic Conference (OIC). Christians view this as an attempt to Islamize the country. This gave rise to Christian, Muslem violence in the country Nigeria.

However, factors like lack of appreciation of different cultures, intolerance, poverty and unemployment also fuel the disintegration in the appreciation of issues of religious diversity in the country. Nigeria with about 150 million people with different cultural backgrounds, religious intolerance is common. Such attitude still may lead to disorder, hostility and confrontation which does not promote national integrations.

Other factors according to (Sen, 2006) are: unemployment, influences of international extremists, shallow media coverage, among others contributed to the promotion of singularity of identities with the attendant

consequence on diversity and multicultural outlook of individual and collective identities in the country". All of these impacts negatively on the tolerance level of Nigerians of diverse religions.

Religion and National Integration

Nigerians are very religious people (Metuah: 1994). There are three major religions in Nigeria: Christianity, Islam and Traditional religion. Kukah (2009:15) opines that "in 1960, the country was divided along religious zones of influence notably the Muslims in the North and the Christians in the South. The traditional religion appears to be un-proselytized religion because it does not go forth seeking converts neither does it pick offense when deserted by its adherents nor assume that its object of worship is superior. It has the rare quality of accommodation and tolerance to other religions (Kukah, 1996:16). This section takes a look at the contributions of religion towards national integration and some questions may arise. To what extent has religion promoted national integration? Has religion being used as a tool of national integration in Nigeria? Attempts should be made to answer these questions.

It seems religion has contributed adversely to the disintegration of Nigeria for the following reasons: During the regime of Babaginda, Nigeria became a member of the Organization of Islamic Conference (OIC) (Ajayi 2008). Though Babaginda's government claimed to have taken the decision on economic reasons: to be able to access the loans available to OIC member

countries at a time Nigeria was in need of finance. Christians viewed this as an attempt to 'Islamize Nigeria' (Simon, 2014:2). This of course was the beginning of Christian versus Muslim open confrontation in Nigeria.

However, the first religious riot motivated by ethnicity between Muslims and Christians was in Kafanchan, old Kaduna state in March 1987 (Asemota, 2013:1). The following month in Ilorin, Kwara state witnessed a conflict when some Christian youths held an Easter procession in a thickly Muslim neighborhood, pointing at houses and singing, "Jesus dey here"? "He dey" (Asemota, 2013: 1). The tension went on and with Zaria, Tafawa Balewa, Zongo Kotaf, Kano and several others (This day live, 24th Thursday April, 2014:2).

Furthermore, when the former central bank governor Mallam Sanusi Lamido Sanusi was suspended due to financial misconduct and replaced by Goodwin Emefiele, a Christian. Only for some groups in the North to start ethno-religious justification for the removal of Sanusi (Nairaland forum 23rd Monday, 2014). Senator David Mark raised an alarm over the issue of some desperate persons using ethnicity and religion to destroy the unity and peace of the Nigerian nation. (www.bellanaija.com/2014/03/26senate-appoints-new-cbn-governor-godwin-emefide. February 10, 2014). He (Mark) concludes by saying he observed that most people tend to use ethnicity and religion for the wrong reasons, stating "what we need now is to embark on serious inter-religious dialogue with the spirit of frankness,

honesty, openness, acceptance and understanding in order to move forward”.
<http://leadership/news/34423/don't-destroy-nigeria-nam-politics-r--->

It will not be an overstatement to state that the national integration of Nigeria as a country is already being compromised. This is justified with the Muslim's call for autonomy. The constitution does not at all raise any religion to a state religion. Yet, this principle was violated when the governors in the Northern state issued authority to Islamize public life. In Zamfara, the first state to introduce a strict form of Sharia, “the government claimed that its religious reform was bringing about major changes, whereas all spheres of public life were being transformed into Islamic oriented institutions” (Muhammed, 2010: 16). This state sponsored Islamization affected non-Muslims as well, “they were subjected to gender separation in hotels and restaurants, in buses and taxis” (Asemota, 2013: 3). All these have hampered national integration in Nigeria even in terms of social, political and economic development. According to Wilson (2012) the tendency of religious groups “to politicize religious activities has made the country more difficult to govern. For example, in March 2006, a protest against the cartoons sanitizing the prophet Muhammed in the north overlapped with anti-third term protest”. Following this, dozens of Christians were killed, sparking revenge attacks in the South especially at Onitsha (The Observer, March 6, 2016:2).

It is has been observed that the greatest damage which religion can wreak on the economy is total decline instead of

rapid growth as loss of lives are usually experienced. Thus, Asometa (2002) puts it, “in 1980-1992, a total of twenty religious riots were recorded and death toll put at 6,775 official figures”. Also, a record of religious crises in the country were put together by Christian Movement of Nigeria reveals that twenty-four riots occurred between 1993-2006 with casualty put as well over 500 lives (Christian Social Movement, 2006: 10). In fact, it could be endless making a list of religious crises in the country as it comes up every day (Akah, 2018). It is not only that lives are lost at each religious riot, but many are usually injured. Scores of children are rendered Orphans at tender age, people are rendered refugees in their own land and these constitute socio-economic problems for the national integration of the country. The current insurgency of Boko Haram is worthy to mention here which had started long ago and had destroyed lives and properties. In terms of damages done to the country by Boko Harm as far as human and material resources are concerned, is unquantifiable. Investors both local and foreigners had fled because no one want to do business in an insecurity risk nation like Nigeria. Presently, is the Fulani herdsmen and farmers which has ravaged the country?

The International community would not invest in the country as long as violence persisted (Awowede, 2000:70). Another negative effect religion has had on the country's integration is the promotion of culture of corruption. Almost, every aspect of society is corrupt and religion which ought to have been the tool to correct this abnormality has failed in this regard. Some

of the pastors and Imans have aided and assisted corruption by tasking their followers to look for money at all cost because poverty is not meant for the children of God, so as 'to help God'. "In churches today, preaching centers on money, prosperity and so on (Ephraim, 2014). Whereas, the Holy Books (both the Bible and Quran) have not taught us that. Religious morals is expected to regulate the entire human life or activities. Religion has led to various religious conflicts. Remarkably among them are the Maitatsine riot of 1980 in Kano and conflicts between the Izala and Tijany in Gombe in 1987 (Larkin, 2009:126). Also, the Bulunkutu riot of October 1982, the various Kaduna riots of 1987, 1988, Jigawa riot 2001 and Lagos-Idi-Araba, 2002. As these were not enough, another riot erupted on 22nd November, 2002 in which about 200 people were reportedly killed, and property worth millions of naira were destroyed (Adamolekun, 2012). This was believed to have been caused due to "blasphemous publication" against the Islamic sect. This happened on the day when "miss world Beauty contest was scheduled to hold in Abuja (Tribune, 26 November, 2002) Alama, (2006:17).

Effects of Ethnicity on National Integration

Ethnicity is a major task confronting the achievement of democracy in Nigeria since independence in 1960. Ethnic sentiment is present almost in all areas of Nigerian political economic and social organizations. In fact, low productivity and ineffectiveness presently experienced in the

country can be attributed to ethnic sentiments. This section looks at the effects of ethnicity on national integration. Nigeria is made up of 250 ethnic groups (Ejikeme, 2016). This therefore implies that Nigeria is multi-lingual and multi-ethnic in nature. These tribal differences have given rise for diverse nature of the Nigerian nation. This indicates that though housed in one country, the ethnic groups do not have identical needs, objectives and aspirations. No wonder (Obafemi Awolowo) opines that 'Nigeria is a mere geographic expression'. 'There is no basis for unity' (Yakubu Gowon). These expressions are real judging from the happenings in the country since independence than the deceit embedded in the slogan of "one Nigeria". Most often, ethnic sentiments are used in place of merit and skills. For instance, in the case of appointment, 'God fatherism' comes in, and one has to favour his people whether they are qualified or not. Ethnicity has been one of the major factors that have seriously reduced the image and glory of Nigerian party politics. The "federal character" principle, which has been enshrined in Nigeria constitution since 1979, seeks to ensure that appointments to public service institutions fairly reflect the linguistic, ethnic, religious and geographical diversity of the country (Adamolekun, et al, 1991:75). Also, the current president Buhari once said that Nigerians should vote on religious and ethnic lines (Efiye, 2015). Whatever the intentions were, these actions and statements could trigger suspicion and crises between the two dominant religious groups. By this definition, it becomes a fact that federal character is a tool for ensuring fairness in

public service over professionalism and good attainment. According to Justcash, 2010:1) “the total systematic collapse in Nigeria’s socio-economic and political environment can be attributed to the federal character practice”. The implication is that Nigeria will have unqualified people in sensitive government positions. It is observed that parties now adopt the principles of federal character as a means of gaining credibility which goes along with ethnic coloration.

Owing to the intrusion of ethnicity into the “federal character” principle, it has given rise to the promotion of incompetent and unqualified civil servants, military, top government officials, among others into the Nigeria system. Also, “the inappropriate application of federal character creates mediocrity, inequality, corruption, lack of transparency and above all tribal dominance by the major ethnic groups (Nusiru, 2008:1) and Chukwuemerie, 2013:3). However, (Momah, 2013:1) affirms that ‘federal character’ as it is currently practiced in Nigeria tend to inculcate cheating rather than emphasize hard work, selflessness and nation-building, the core values which our founding fathers lived by”. The demand and desperation for the creation of states and local governments in the country have been informed by ethnic sentiments and marginalization (Suberu, 2006:15). The effects of ethnicity could be noticed in the area of allocation of national resources. For instance, in the first republic due to the fact that the control of government was in the hands of the North such opportunity was used to allocate much funds to the Northern parts at expense of the South. Ethnicity had

affected the Nigerian policy because it heightens political struggle and competition in electoral contest. The activities of the Northern People’s Congress (NPC) in the first Republics when the North insisted that its candidates must win at all cost, to actualize this, some Northern candidates were returned unopposed even before the commencement of the general elections (<https://www/alsadiq.lecture.pdf>).

Nevertheless, the various ‘ethno-religious’ disturbances were strong force for socio-political instability, and national disintegration. They described the gross inadequacy and ineffectiveness of the state security, security of lives and property could not be guaranteed. The climate of insecurity created by violent conflict deter investment. The economy becomes stagnant and democracy divide equally become an illusion. However, the growing incidence of ethno-religious crisis in Nigeria is worrisome and if ethno-religious conflicts are not reduced now and completely, the memories from such could create future conflicts. Thus, what is new in this research is that religion contributes largely to national disintegration in Nigeria, and religion will kill Nigerians if is not tamed.

Recommendations

For the promotion of Nigeria’s national integration, the paper recommends the following:

- I. The government should respond to religious crisis on time in order to arrest the situation.

- II. Fanaticism in religion must be minimized in order to pave way for re-designing the Nigerian society.
- III. Leaders should strengthen existing policies that promote tolerance of other people's culture.
- IV. The knowledge of Nigerian nation and its citizens in terms of geography, history, sociology and anthropological set ups and other basic information that can nurture the spirit of empathy are grossly deficient. This is why currently even basic arguments on general issues of governance are easily ethicized or religionized to the detriment of the collective good.
- V. Nigerians must learn to love one another and imbibe the spirit of patriotism and nationalism.
- VI. The 'federal character' principle which encourages discrimination and indigenization should be de-emphasized by the government and all.
- VII. Since Nigeria is a multi-religious, multi-ethnic and heterogeneous nation, secularity should be the best option in order to promote national integration and development.

Conclusion

This research has so far revealed that ethno-religious conflicts are inevitable in a multi-ethnic and multi-religious society like Nigeria. It is not an over statement to state that ethno-religious conflicts retard national integration, soils social relations and destabilizes the economy of Nigeria nation. Ethno-religious bigotry in Nigeria have become a hinge of various forms of

nationalism. The occurrences of ethnic and religious conflicts in Nigeria are alarming and requires urgent and continued attention. The use of ethnicity, and religion should rather unite us as Nigerians in order to promote peace, peaceful co-existence and unity. Okwueze (2003) sees peace as an enterprise of justice, peace results from that harmony built into human society by its divine founder and actualized by man as they thirst after ever-greater justice". The reverse of this has consequences for Nigeria as there were "ethno-religious" crises that claimed so many lives and property. The spate of ethno-religious crises in Nigeria since independence has produced a catalogue that resulted in an estimated loss of over three million lives and unquantifiable psychological and maternal damages (NIPSS, 2004).

In fact, ethnicity and religion have affected negatively on the development of the nation in many ways namely: socially, politically, and economically. In order to proffer solution that brings peace and promote national integration, both religious and political leaders must begin to emphasis the need to embrace peace. As the country remains multi-religious and ethno-linguistic pluralism, secularity is the best option that can uphold peace and harmony. It is certain that if Nigeria was not colonized, the issue of ethnic sentiment among the different ethnic groups would have been very impossible. The spirit of indigene-settler and 'federal character' phenomenon should be discouraged by the federal government. Also, fanaticism in religion should be reduced in order to pave way for re-designing Nigerian society.

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